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Cancer Risk Assessment from Exposure to Trihalomethanes in Drinking Water and Swimming Pool Water

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Abstract

The objective of the paper is to investigate the concentration of trihalomethanes (THMs) and their compounds (chloroform, bromodichloromethane, dibromochloromethane, and bromoform) in drinking water (DW) and swimming pool water (SPW) and to assess the cancer risk among citizens living in the City of Novi Sad. The investigation was related to 931 DW and 146 SPW samples analyzed by the Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina in 2017. Static headspace sampling and gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry was used to determine the THMs. The cancer risk assessment was done by applying the United States Environmental Protection Agency methodology. The concentration of total THMs, chloroform, bromodichloromethane, dibromochloromethane, and bromoform in DW was 23.99 ± 11.35 , 9.79 ± 5.94 , 6.98 ± 3.49 , 6.80 ± 3.19 , and 6.80 ± 3.19 mg/l, respectively, whereas those in SPW were 130.85 ± 135.58 , 128.27 ± 136.40 , 3.66 ± 3.33 , 0.64 ± 1.60 , and 0.00 , respectively. The concentration of THMs in DW did not exceed the proposed value (100 mg/l) but did it in 40% SPW samples. The total cancer risk of THMs in DW and SPW was found to be acceptable ($1.56E-06$ and $6.66E-06$, respectively). The dominant compound in total THMs in DW was dibromochloromethane, whereas in SPW chloroform. Adequate risk management, dominantly in SPW, is necessary.

Keywords: Water, Pool, Swimming pool, Public Health, Environmental Medicine, Risk, Trihalomethanes.

Introduction

Water is essential for life, and ensuring equal access to a sufficient amount of safe drinking water, maintaining personal and general hygiene, and nutrition is defined as a basic human right (WHO, 2017a; UN 2016). It is also important to highlight the role of water for recreation and sports in/on water, i.e., outdoor/indoor pools, rivers, and lakes, in maintaining and improving human health (WHO, 2006). Whether for drinking, maintaining personal and general hygiene and nutrition, or for recreation and sports, the use of water is permitted only if the drinking or recreational water is safe. It means the absence of microbiological, physical, and chemical hazards that can cause the disease among the population (WHO, 2006, 2017a; Bartram et al., 2009; USEPA, 2012).

The World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) are emphases that 2.1 billion people do not have safe drinking water and that 844 million people do not have access to safe water (WHO and UNICEF, 2017).

The drinking water safety and the recreational water management are on the international level regulated by WHO and the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) recommendations, by European Union (EU) Directives, and on the national level by regulations defined by countries (WHO, 2006, 2017a; USEPA, 2012, 2018; Council Directive 1998, 2000, 2006). In the Republic of Serbia (RS), drinking water safety and pool water health management is under the patronage of the Ministry of Health regulated by national laws and bylaws („Official Gazette of RS” 41/2009, 97/2017, 42/1998, 44/1999, 28/2019, 136/2020). They recognize the scope, type, and frequency of analyzes, limit values for the proposed parameters, but not the risk assessment.

Among chemical hazards, it is recommended to monitor those characteristics of areas or countries, among which for the region of Southern and Central Europe, stand out arsenic, fluorides, nitrates, nitrites, iodine, disinfection byproducts (WHO, 2017a; Schmoll, 2018). Chemical hazards, when it comes to pool water, include an increase in the concentration

of disinfection byproducts (residual chlorine, total trihalomethanes, and its four compounds, bromates, bromides, cyanuric acid) and organic or inorganic compounds, depending on the type of water, method and efficiency of purification, maintenance of water supply systems and the number of users (WHO, 2006).

Disinfection is essential for ensuring water safety (WHO, 2017a). The most commonly used disinfection method is chemical with chlorine preparations (WHO, 2005, 2017a; Sbutega Milošević et al. 2014; Safe Drinking Water Committee, 1987). Trihalomethanes are formed in water as a result of disinfection with chlorine preparations. The rate and degree of trihalomethanes formation in water depends on the concentration of the used chlorine preparation (usually hypochlorite) and organic matter, bromide, temperature, and pH value (WHO, 2017a). The total trihalomethanes, which are determinate in water, is presented as the sum of four compounds: chloroform, bromodichloromethane, dibromochloromethane, and bromoform. Chloroform is the most often formed trihalomethanes compound (WHO, 2017a). The formation of other brominated compounds (bromodichloromethane, dibromochloromethane, and bromoform) depends on the bromide concentration. It is assumed that trihalomethanes formed in water are intensively transferred to the air due to their easy volatility.

Human exposure to trihalomethanes is predominantly related to the ingestion of drinking water (WHO, 2017a; IARC, 2013), followed by dermal absorption and inhalation during showering, bathing, and recreation (drinking water, pool water), especially in indoor pools with inadequate ventilation and insufficient air volume. A susceptible population is the more exposed one, i.e., athletes, recreationists, patients who use hydrotherapy, children, pregnant women, and chronically ill people with liver, kidneys, or nasal mucosa diseases.

The limit value for total trihalomethanes and their compounds in drinking water (WHO, 2017a) according to WHO recommendations are 300 mg/l, for both bromoform and bromodichloromethane 60 mg/l, for dibromochloromethane 100 mg/l and for total trihalomethanes it is recommended that the sum of the four trihalomethanes compounds divided by their limit values, should be less or equal to one. In the EU (Council Directive, 1998), the value is prescribed only for total trihalomethanes (100 mg/l). In the USA, according to USEPA, the limit value is set to 80 mg/l (USEPA, 2010). In the RS ("Official Gazette of RS" 42/1998, 44/1999, 28/2019), the limit value for total trihalomethanes is 100 mg/l, for chloroform 40 mg/l, while for bromodichloromethane prescribed limit value of 1.5 mg/l can be increased up to 25 mg/l if the chloroform concentration is reduced to 30 mg/l.

Limit values for trihalomethanes in pool water are rarely prescribed, mostly they refer to the concentration of free and bound chlorine (WHO, 2006; USEPA, 2012; Council Directive, 1998). In the RS ("Official Gazette of RS" 97/2017), a limit value for total trihalomethanes is set to 100 µg/l.

Ensuring drinking water safety requires a comprehensive approach and engagement of all participants in the chain of water production and consumption, defined by risk analysis (WHO, 2017a). Risk analysis consists of three main closely related parts: risk assessment, risk communication, and risk management (SRPS EN 15975-5:2015; Benford, 2001). Risk assessment is a science-based evaluation of potential adverse effects on human health resulting from exposure to hazards (WHO, 2017a). It consists of four steps: hazard identification (microbiological, physical, and chemical), hazard characterization (qualitative/quantitative analysis), assessment exposures (qualitative/quantitative), and risk characterization (qualitative, quantitative, and semi-quantitative).

Semi-quantitative risk characterization is the most commonly used analysis due to its comprehensibility and feasibility; even it is less reliable than quantitative (WHO, 2017a). On the other hand, one of the most reliable methods (USEPA, 1988) for risk characterization is quantitative characterization. It assesses the individual risk for cancers or diseases after the chronic, sub-chronic, and acute exposure to known hazards via different exposure routes (ingestion, dermal absorption, inhalation). Chronic exposure means exposure lasting from seven years to life, sub-chronic from two weeks to seven years, and acute is currently present, lasting up to two weeks. The risk is quantitatively assessed for all routes of exposure, and a simple sum of all determines the total risk. The total risk is the risk of the carcinogenic effects of the examined hazards. If the total risk values are in the range from E-04 to E-07, it is considered acceptable (USEPA, 1988; NRC, 2001).

The overall risk of non-carcinogenic effects of the examined hazards is determined based on the overall hazard index (USEPA, 1988). It represents an assessment of the probability of an individual becoming ill due to exposure to hazards. The overall risk of non-carcinogenic effects is also assessed for all exposure routes and in line with the length of exposure. Thus there are defined the chronic hazard index (for chronic exposure lasting from seven years to life) and the sub-chronic hazard index (for sub-chronic exposure lasting from two weeks to seven years), while for acute exposures lasting less than two weeks, assessments are based on toxicological hazard properties (USEPA, 1987 a, b, 1988). According to the routes and length of exposure, the sum of individual hazard indices gives

the total hazard index. If the hazard index values are <1, it is unlikely that the examined danger will cause the occurrence of the disease even among the vulnerable population (USEPA, 1988).

Numerous studies have been conducted worldwide on human health risk assessment caused by exposure to total trihalomethanes and its compounds (Panyakapo et al., 2008; Viana et al., 2009; Font-Ribera et al., 2010; Salas et al. 2013). However, in the RS, the risk assessment for various drinking and pool water hazards has not been recognized. Individual scientific and epidemiological research in the RS has shown that there are microbiological (thermotolerant microorganisms), and especially chemical (arsenic, nitrates, and nitrites) hazards in drinking water on the territory of the South Bačka Administrative District, which risk after the chronic exposure was quantified as high (Bijelović et al., 2017). Also, the research of small water supply systems on the territory of the RS showed that arsenic is a hazard in drinking water on the territory of AP Vojvodina, while in Central, Eastern, and Western Serbia, microorganisms, especially *Escherichia coli*, are the most common hazard (WHO, 2017b). Considering that the existing data on risk assessment on the territory of the RS do not refer to systematized data on population exposure to trihalomethanes and its carcinogenic risk, the need to determine them and recognize the methodology to implement it in national regulations, strategies, or action plans in the field of public health, is especially emphasized.

This work aimed to determine whether trihalomethanes in drinking water and pool water pose a danger to public health, i.e., whether exposure to trihalomethanes in drinking water and pool water represents a health risk to the population of the City of Novi Sad.

Materials and Methods

The investigation was conducted as a cross-sectional study on the City of Novi Sad territory during 2017. It included analyzing 932 samples of purified and disinfected drinking water originating from the municipality drinking water factory and analyzing 146 purified and disinfected water samples from three public indoor swimming pools. The drinking water is disinfected with chlorine preparations and ozone, while the swimming pool samples are disinfected only with chlorine preparations.

Sampling, transport, analyses and assessing the results was done according to accredited, standardize and proposed national methodology by authorized and accredited public health institution situated in the City of Novi Sad (Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina). The static headspace sampling and gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (reference method ISO 10301) were used to determine the THMs and their four compounds (chloroform, bromodichlormethane, dibromochlormethane, and bromoform). The quantification limit of individual trihalomethanes was 1 mg/l. Total trihalomethanes (mg/l) were calculated as the sum of four THMs compounds.

Assessing the drinking water quality, as well as pool water safety, was done following national law and by-law (WHO, 2017a; Council Directive, 2006; Official Gazette of RS, 41/2009; 97/2017, 42/1998, 44/1999, 28/2019, 136/2020), where proposed concentration for THMs in drinking water and pool water is set to 100 mg/l and proposed concentration for chloroform and bromodichlormethane is set to 40 mg/l and 1.5 mg/l, respectively.

Semi-quantitative risk characterization (WHO, 2017a) takes in to account the likelihood (almost certainly, likely, moderately, unlikely, and rarely) and the severity of the consequences (insignificant, minor, moderate, major, and catastrophic) of the identified hazards on human health and/or the environment (Table 1). After the semi-quantitative assessment,

Table 1: The scoring matrix for risk ranking by semi-quantitative method.

Likelihood/ Severity of consequences (with rating)	Insignificant (no impact), rating 1	Minor* (compliance impact), rating 2	Moderate** (Aesthetic impact), rating 3	Major*** (regulatory impact), rating 4	Catastrophic [§] (public health impact), rating 5
Almost certain (once per day), rating 5	5	10	15	20	25
Likely (once per week), rating 4	4	8	12	16	20
Moderately likely (once per month), rating 3	3	6	9	12	15
Unlikely (once per year), rating 2	2	4	6	8	10
Rare (once in a 5 years), rating 1	1	2	3	4	5

Legend: *Minor: Minor aesthetic impact causing dissatisfaction but not likely to lead to use of alternative less safe sources; **Moderate: Major aesthetic impact possibly resulting in use of alternative but unsafe water sources; ***Major: Morbidity expected from consuming water; [§] Catastrophic: Mortality expected from consuming water

the risk is characterized as low (<6), medium (6-9), high (10-15), and very high (>15), meaning that risk does not influence population, that the risk is presented as a need for using the alternative less safe drinking water sources, that the risk influences morbidity of sensitive population and that the risk influences mortality of population, respectively.

Quantitative risk characterization for total cancer risk concerning ingestion and dermal absorption (USEPA, 2005; Paopuree et al., 2018) from drinking water and swimming pool water, not an inhalation, taking into account the average and highest THMs concentration, was done by using the following formulas (Table 2).

Table 2: Assessing the quantitative risk characterization for total cancer risk concerning ingestion and dermal absorption.

Risk and pathways	Formulas
Total cancer risk	$Total\ cancer\ risk = CDI \times SF; AD \times SF; \Sigma Risk$
Ingestion from drinking water	$CDI = \frac{CW \times IR \times EF \times ED}{BW \times AT}$
Ingestion from swimming pool water	$CDI = \frac{CW \times CR \times ET \times EF \times ED}{BW \times AT}$
Dermal absorption from drinking water and swimming pool water	$AD = \frac{CW \times SA \times PC \times ET \times EF \times ED \times CF}{BW \times AT}$

Legend: *CDI – chronic daily intake; SF – slope factor; AD – absorbed dose; CW - concentration value; IR – ingestion rate; EF – exposure frequency; ED – exposure duration; CR – contact rate; ET – exposure time; SA – skin surface area available for contact; PC – chemical specific dermal permeability constant; CF – volumetric conversion factor for water; BW – body weight; AT – average time.

In the absence of national data, the internationally recognized ones (USEPA, 1988) were used for calculating, as follows: 2 l/day for IR; 365 events/year for EF; 70 years for ED; 70 kg for BW; 50 l/h for CR; 1 h/event for ET (ingestion) and 2.6 h/event for ET (dermal absorption); 7 events/year for EF; 1,815 m² for SA; 1 l/1000 cm³=1 for CF; for AT for non-carcinogenic effect as Lc (30 mg/kg BW), ED x 365 days/year; and for AT for carcinogenic effect Lc (30 mg/kg BW), 70 years x 365 days/year where Lc is defined as oral no-observed-adverse-effect-level (NOAEL).

Total cancer risk was characterized due to:

- type of water (drinking water, swimming pool water, both),
- pathways for THMs uptake (ingestion, dermal absorption) and
- population habits of using the drinking water and swimming pool water (a group which is/ which is not using the swimming pools).

The values of total cancer risk in interval E-04-E-07 was assessed as acceptable (HSE and EPA, 2011).

Chronic Hazard Index for THMs compounds due to ingestion and dermal absorption from drinking water and swimming pool water was calculated by using the following formula:

$$Chronic\ Hazard\ Index = \frac{CDI1}{RfD1} + \frac{CDI2}{RfD2} + \frac{CDI3}{RfD3} + \dots < 1,$$

where CDI represent chronic daily intake, RfD chronic reference dose for hazard and SF slope factor. RfD for dibromchloromethane and bromoform is 0,02 mg/

kg/day, while for chloroform and bromdichlormethane is 0,01 mg/kg/day (USEPA 1987 a, b).

The values of the chronic hazard index <1 were considered acceptable, meaning that it is unlikely that the examined danger will cause the disease's occurrence even among the vulnerable population.

Results and Discussion

The concentration of THMs and its compounds in drinking water

The concentration of THMs and their compounds in drinking water was in a range of 2.2-61.6 mg/l without exceeding the proposed value (Table 3). Comparing the obtained values of concentrations of THMs in drinking water on the territory of the City of Novi Sad with international data (Luks-Betlej et al., 2002; Egorov et al., 2003; Panyakapo et al., 2008; Baytak et al., 2008; Viana RB et al., 2009; Ristoiu et al., 2009; Font-Ribera et al., 2010; Salas et al., 2013; UNECE and WHO, 2013; Summerhayes, 2014; Abdullah, 2014; Szegedi Vizmu Zrt, 2018), it can be concluded that the average concentration of THMs is similar to the average values or ranges of average concentrations in Poland (2.19-36.91 mg/l), Egypt (12 -74 mg/l) and Thailand (23.13 mg/l), lower than the average values or range of average concentrations in Spain (117 mg/l), Brazil (105-141 mg/l), Turkey (43.6 mg/l), Romania (10-80 mg/l), Russia (205±70 mg/l) and Australia (66.8 mg/l, with a range of 14.5-330.7 mg/l) and higher than the average values or range of average concentrations in Hungary (2 mg/l) and the Czech Republic.

Table 3: The concentration of trichalomethanes and its compounds in drinking water, the City of Novi Sad, 2017.

Statistical indicator	Total trihalomethanes	Chloroform	Bromdichlormethane	Dibromchlormethane	Bromoform
Average value (µg/l)	23.99	9.80	6.98	6.80	6.80
Minimal value (µg/l)	2.20	<1	<1	<1	<1
Maximal value (µg/l)	61.60	31.80	21.80	18.60	18.60
Standard deviation	11.35	5.94	3.49	3.19	3.19
% of exceeding the guideline value	0.00	0.00	-	-	-

Legend: „-“, there are no guideline values; thus, it is impossible to determine the exceedings

The concentration of THMs and its compounds in swimming pool water

The concentration of THMs and their compounds in swimming pool water was in a range of 14.7-870.7 mg/l with exceeding the proposed value for THMs in 58 (39.73%) samples (Table 4). The determined concentrations of THMs and chloroform in the swimming pool water were higher than those determined in drinking water. In contrast, the values of brominated trihalomethanes in the swimming pool water were lower than in the drinking water. Comparing the obtained concentrations of THMs in

the swimming pool water on the territory of the City of Novi Sad with international data (Panyakapo et al., 2008; Dyck et al., 2011; Simard et al., 2013; Drev et al., 2015; Tardif et al., 2016; Bozym et al., 2017), it can be concluded that the average concentration of THMs is similar to the average values or ranges of average concentrations in London (57-223 mg/l), Italy (6.8-134 mg/l), Portugal (10-155 mg/l) and Canada (17.5-215 mg/l) and higher than average values or range of average concentrations in Spain (48.96±9.84 mg/l), Germany (25.6 mg/l) and Thailand (46.72 mg/l).

Table 4: The concentration of trichalomethanes and its compounds in indoor swimming pool water, the City of Novi Sad, 2017.

Statistical indicator	Total trihalomethanes	Chloroform	Bromdichlormethane	Dibromchlormethane	Bromoform
Average value (µg/l)	130.85	128.27	3.66	0.60	0.00
Minimal value (µg/l)	14.70	14.70	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maximal value (µg/l)	870.70	865.80	22.00	12.70	0.00
Standard deviation	135.59	136.40	3.33	1.60	0.00
% of exceeding the guideline value	39.73	-	-	-	-

Legend: „-“, there are no guideline values; thus, it is impossible to determine the exceedings

Semi-quantitative risk characterization

The concentration of THMs and their compounds in drinking water which were analyzed once per week (rating 4), did not exceed the proposed level, so consequences were insignificant (rating 1), and the risk (rating 4x1=4) was assessed as low due to semi-quantitative methodology.

The concentration of THMs and their compounds in swimming pool water which was analyzed once per week (rating 4), exceeded the proposed level, mostly chloroform, in 40% of controlled samples, so consequences were major with having an impact on human health (rating 4) and the risk (rating 4x4=16) was assessed as very high in line with WHO methodology for semi-quantitative risk analyses.

Quantitative risk characterization

The cancer risk from THMs in drinking water after the ingestion and dermal absorption of average and maximum concentrations of THMs and its compounds was 1.07E-06 and 3.11E-06, respectively, while the risk from THMs in swimming pool water after the ingestion and dermal absorption of average and maximum concentrations of THMs and its compounds was 4.88E-07 and 3.55E-06, respectively (Table 5).

The total cancer risk from THMs ingested and dermally absorbed both from drinking water and swimming pool water, based on the average and maximum concentrations of THMs and their compounds, were 1.56E-06 and 6.66E-06, respectively (Table 6).

Table 5: Cancer risk caused by exposure to THMs and its compounds by ingestion and dermal absorption from drinking water and swimming pool water in the City of Novi Sad, 2017.

Total THMs and compounds	Concentration (µg/l)	CDI (mg/kg BW/day)	AD (mg/kg BW/day)	CDI Total= CDI+AD (mg/kg BW/day)	Slope factor (kg*day/mg)	Risk
Assessment based on average concentration in drinking water						
Chloroform	9.80	9.33E-06	3.76E-08	9.37E-06	0.0061	5.71E-08
Bromdichlormethane	6.98	6.65E-06	2.68E-08	6.67E-06	0.062	4.14E-07
Dibromchlormethane	6.80	6.48E-06	2.61E-08	6.50E-06	0.084	5.46E-07
Bromoform	6.80	6.48E-06	2.61E-08	6.50E-06	0.0079	5.14E-08
Total Risk						1.07E-06
Assessment based on maximum concentration in drinking water						
Chloroform	31.8	3.03E-05	1.22E-07	3.04E-05	0.0061	1.85E-07
Bromdichlormethane	21.8	2.08E-05	8.36E-08	2.08E-05	0.062	1.29E-06
Dibromchlormethane	18.6	1.77E-05	7.13E-08	1.78E-05	0.084	1.49E-06
Bromoform	18.6	1.77E-05	7.13E-08	1.78E-05	0.0079	1.41E-07
Total Risk						3.11E-06
Assessment based on average concentration in swimming pool water						
Chloroform	128.27	5.86E-05	4.92E-07	5.91E-05	0.0061	3.60E-07
Bromdichlormethane	3.66	1.67E-06	1.41E-08	1.69E-06	0.062	1.05E-07
Dibromchlormethane	0.60	2.76E-07	2.32E-09	2.78E-07	0.084	2.34E-08
Bromoform	-	-	-	-	0.0079	-
Total Risk						4.88E-07
Assessment based on maximum concentration in swimming pool water						
Chloroform	865.80	3.95E-04	3.32E-06	3.99E-04	0.0061	2.43E-06
Bromdichlormethane	22.00	1.00E-05	8.44E-08	1.01E-05	0.062	6.28E-07
Dibromchlormethane	12.70	5.80E-06	4.87E-08	5.85E-06	0.084	4.91E-07
Bromoform	-	-	-	-	0.0079	-
Total Risk						3.55E-06

Legend: CDI-chronic daily intake; AD - absorbed dose through dermal contact; CDI Total – total chronic daily intake, based on ingestion and dermal absorption, without inhalation; Slope factor – factor defined within scientific literature

Table 6: Total cancer risk caused by exposure to THMs and its compounds by ingestion and dermal absorption from drinking water and swimming pool water in the City of Novi Sad, 2017.

Total THMs and compounds	Total risk from drinking water	Total risk from swimming pool water	Total cancer risk
Assessment based on average concentration			
Chloroform	5.71E-08	3.60E-07	4.17E-07
Bromdichlormethane	4.14E-07	1.05E-07	5.18E-07
Dibromchlormethane	5.46E-07	2.34E-08	5.70E-07
Bromoform	5.14E-08	0.00E+00	5.14E-08
Total risk	1.07E-06	4.88E-07	1.56E-06
Assessment based on maximum concentration			
Chloroform	1.85E-07	2.43E-06	2.62E-06
Bromdichlormethane	1.29E-06	6.28E-07	1.92E-06
Dibromchlormethane	1.49E-06	4.91E-07	1.99E-06
Bromoform	1.41E-07	0.00E+00	1.41E-07
Total risk	3.11E-06	3.55E-06	6.66E-06

Semi-quantitative risk assessment was performed based on individually determined concentrations of THMs and their compounds, taking into account exceeded proposed levels of THMs compounds and their carcinogenetic and the frequency of determining the concentration of THMs in water. As the WHO recommendations (WHO, 2017a) explain, semi-quantitative assessment is easy to perform, easy to interpret, but still insufficiently reliable, especially when there is an excess of the examined indicators' concentrations, regardless of

the frequency of their proof. This is the case with the identified risk arising from the intake of THMs and their compounds from drinking water in the City of Novi Sad. Concerning that the guidelines values were not exceeded in the one-week frequency of analyzes, the risk was low. The risk would be small even if the frequency of analyzes were more or less frequent. It seems that only the carcinogenicity of controlled hazards would increase the risk (IARC, 2013, 2018; USEPA, 1988). So, the result of a semi-quantitative assessment should serve as a basis

for further analysis, i.e., performing quantitative risk assessments that will reliably confirm or deny the results of semi-quantitative analyzes. This especially refers to the presence and concentration of THMs in the swimming pool water in the City of Novi Sad, where, related to semi-quantitative characterization, the risk was very high. Still, after the quantitative risk assessment, it was found acceptable. Therefore, the semi-quantitative analysis should be done regularly, perhaps by monitoring drinking water or annually swimming pool water. The assessed high or very high risk should be further examined using a quantitative risk assessment method.

The probability that exposure to THMs and their compounds will cause cancer after exposure from drinking water in one individual in the City of Novi Sad is 1 in 1.000.000 ($1.07E-06$) for average and 3 in 1.000.000 ($3.11E-06$) for maximum concentrations, and the total risk, relative to USEPA recommendations (USEPA, 2005), is acceptable. The total risk from THMs and their compounds in drinking water, defined as acceptable (Panyakapo et al., 2008; Baytak et al., 2008; Viana et al., 2009; Font-Ribera et al., 2010), was also determined in Turkey ($1.18E-04$), Taiwan ($1.80E-04$), Hong Kong ($1.99E-05$), Thailand ($4.65E-05$ for average; $9.40E-05$ for maximum values) and Brazil (in Fortaleza a total of $2.50E-05$ for ingestion, in the city center $1.22E-05$).

The probability that exposure to THMs and their compounds from swimming pool water would cause cancer in one individual in the City of Novi Sad is 48 per 10.000.000 or 0.48 per 1.000.000, or less than one per 1.000.000 ($4.88E-07$), for average and three per 1.000.000 ($3.55E-06$) for maximum concentrations. The risk concerning the USEPA recommendations (WHO, 2017) is acceptable. After exposure to the swimming pool water for the City of Novi Sad population, the determining cancer risk is lower than the risk of ingestion and dermal absorption of THMs from drinking water (10 times lower for average and equal to maximum values). A study by Panyakapo M. and authors in Thailand (Panyakapo et al., 2008) showed that the total risk in indoor pool water for both average ($1.38E-03$) and maximum values ($7.53E-04$) was higher than our data and is unacceptable. Another group of authors from Thailand which studied the total cancer risk for users divided into six groups (adult swimmers, adult non-swimmers, young swimmers, young non-swimmers, trainers, and support staff), concluded that the total risk for all six groups ranged from $1.23E-04$ to $8.36E-03$, that the risk was unacceptable and the highest for support staff (Paopuree et al., 2018). All of the above indicates that the total cancer risk related to swimming pool water depends on the quality of the incoming water, treatment methods, and especially pool water disinfection, system maintenance, construction

characteristics of the facility, especially the volume of indoor pool facilities, number of users, compliance with basic house rules, regular monitoring of the swimming pool water safety and education of both the owner and staff, as well as pool users.

Total cancer risk depending on structure of THMs

In the structure of THMs, dibromochloromethane, was the dominant compound in total cancer risk for drinking water and in total risk for both types of water for average concentration (Figure 1). Simultaneously, the chloroform was a dominant compound in total cancer risk for swimming pool water and in total risk for both types of water for maximum concentration (Figure 2). THM compounds and the fact that the largest contribution to the total cancer risk from drinking water was determined for dibromochloromethane, which is defined (IARC, 2018) as an unclassified carcinogen for humans (Group 3), the estimated risk can be further considered acceptable. In contrast to our results, research in Brazil and Thailand showed that bromodichloromethanes (carcinogens of group 2B) and then dibromochloromethanes dominate the total risk from drinking water among THMs compounds (Panyakapo et al., 2008; Font-Ribera et al., 2010).

Figure 1: The structure of THMs compounds for average concentrations in total risk from drinking water and swimming pool water and total cancer risk for both type of water in the City of Novi Sad, 2017.

Figure 2: The structure of THMs compounds for the maximum concentrations in total risk from drinking water and swimming pool water and total cancer risk for both type of water in the City of Novi Sad, 2017.

On the other hand, the largest contribution to the total cancer risk from swimming pool water was determined for chloroform (73.79% for average and 68.48% for maximum values) and the smallest for dibromochloromethane (4.79% for average and 13.83 % for maximum values). At the same time, bromoform was not detected in the pool water. In most of the countries, as well as in the City of Novi Sad, chloroform with its maximum concentrations, was the most common THMs compound as in drinking water, so in indoor swimming pool water, as well as the structure of the THMs compounds in the drinking water in the most of the countries, including the City of Novi Sad, was dominated by brominated trihalomethanes (Luks-Betlej et al., 2002; Egorov et al., 2003; Panyakapo et al., 2008; Baytak et al., 2008; Viana et al., 2009; Ristou et al., 2009; Font-Ribera et al., 2010; HSE and EPA, 2011; UNECE and WHO, 2013; Summerhayes, 2014; Abdullah, 2014; Szegedi Vizmu Zrt., 2018). Also, across the world, an indoor swimming pool water, chloroform was isolated as the most common (98%) compound and also as dominant compound in the structure of THMs (Panyakapo et al., 2008; Dyck et al., 2011; Simard et al., 2013; Drev et al., 2015; Tardif et al., 2016; Bozym et al., 2017; v.Veldhoven et al., 2018). Despite the almost immeasurable total risk for average values of THMs in swimming pool water in the City of Novi Sad, it is necessary to keep in mind the results of total risk based on the maximum THMs and its compounds concentration, especially that the chloroform, known as a possible carcinogen (Group 2B) (IARC, 2018), was the most detected THMs compound. That is why it is necessary to define preventive measures, especially in accident situations that lead to an increase in THMs and their compounds' concentration.

The pathways for THMs uptake and total cancer risk

The ingestion is the dominant pathway for THMs

and their compounds uptake, both for average (99.46%) and maximum (99.37%) concentration (Table 7). Due to ingestion and dermal absorption of THMs and their compounds from drinking water and swimming pool water in the City of Novi Sad, the risk to human health was assessed based on analysis of individual, average, and maximum determined concentrations. The contribution to the total cancer risk resulting from inhalation intake has not been determined due to the lack of data. Some studies also do not take into account the inhaled intake of THMs, justified by sufficient space capacity and ventilation of indoor pool facilities that lower the concentration of trihalomethane in the air to a minimum or immeasurable concentrations (USEPA, 2005), while in other studies (USEPA, 1988; Dyck et al., 2011; Simard et al., 2013; Tardif et al., 2013; WHO, 2017), risk assessment is based on analysis of all three types of exposure (ingestion, dermal absorption, inhalation). Research in the City of Novi Sad has shown that the ingestion of THMs and their compounds from drinking water and swimming pool water has been the dominant pathway. Given that ingestion is the dominant pathway, which is also the least dangerous one for trihalomethane (IARC, 2018), the total cancer risk can be further considered acceptable. Ingestion as the dominant route of intake of THMs and its compounds from drinking water has been proven in various epidemiological studies and cross-sectional studies (Panyakapo et al., 2008; Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2000; Dyck et al., 2011; Simard et al., 2013; Abdullah, 2014; v.Veldhoven et al., 2018), while for pool water dermal contact has been singled out as the dominant route of intake in most countries (Canada, Thailand, Spain, United Kingdom, United States). A review study by a group of authors from USEPA points out that dermal absorption and inhalation are the main routes for THMs exposure related to the possible cancer development among the exposed population (Richardson et al., 2007).

Table 7: The dominant pathways of THMs and its compound uptake from drinking water and swimming pool water in the City of Novi Sad, 2017.

Total THMs and compounds	Ingestion	% of total cancer risk due to ingestion	Dermal absorption	% of total cancer risk due to dermal absorption	Total cancer risk
Assessment based on average concentration					
Chloroform	4.14E-07	99.23	3.23E-09	0.77	4.18E-07
Bromdichlormethane	5.16E-07	99.51	2.54E-09	0.49	5.18E-07
Dibromchlormethane	5.68E-07	99.58	2.39E-09	0.42	5.70E-07
Bromoform	5.12E-08	99.60	2.06E-10	0.40	5.14E-08
Total Risk	1.55E-06	99.46	8.36E-09	0.54	1.56E-06
Assessment based on maximum concentration					
Chloroform	2.59E-06	99.20	2.10E-08	0.80	2.62E-06
Bromdichlormethane	1.91E-06	99.46	1.04E-08	0.54	1.92E-06
Dibromchlormethane	1.97E-06	99.49	1.01E-08	0.51	1.98E-06
Bromoform	1.40E-07	99.60	5.63E-10	0.40	1.40E-07
Total Risk	6.62E-06	99.37	4.21E-08	0.63	6.66E-06

Total cancer risk depending on population habits of using the drinking water and swimming pool water

Populations habits of using the drinking water and swimming pools have shown that total cancer risk is higher among the population which, besides drinking water from municipality water factory, was using swimming pools, as for average concentration (1.56E-06 vs. 1.07E-06), as for maximum ones (6.66E-06 vs. 3.11E-06), without statistical significance ($p=0.499$ for average and $p=0.498$ for maximum concentration)

(Table 8). For both groups of residents, whether they were using or not public swimming pools, the risk is acceptable, with the fact that THMs and their compounds from the swimming pool water, predominantly ingested, contribute to the magnitude of the total cancer risk. Similar results were obtained in Thailand, where residents who bathed and recreated in the public swimming pools and drank water from the public water supply had a higher total cancer risk, with the total cancer risk from the swimming pool water being higher, and the dominant pathway dermal absorption (Panyakapo et al., 2008).

Table 8: Total cancer risk caused by population habits of using the drinking water and swimming pool water in the City of Novi Sad, 2017.

Total THMs and compounds	Total cancer risk among population which was not using swimming pools*	Total cancer risk among population which was using swimming pools*
Assessment based on average concentration		
Chloroform	5.71E-08	4.17E-07
Bromdichlormethane	4.14E-07	5.18E-07
Dibromchlormethane	5.46E-07	5.70E-07
Bromoform	5.14E-08	5.14E-08
Total cancer risk	1.07E-06	1.56E-06
Assessment based on maximum concentration		
Chloroform	1.85E-07	2.62E-06
Bromdichlormethane	1.29E-06	1.92E-06
Dibromchlormethane	1.49E-06	1.99E-06
Bromoform	1.41E-07	1.41E-07
Total cancer risk	3.11E-06	6.66E-06

Legend: *Considers population with no habits of using swimming pools, meaning that the total cancer risk from THMs compounds depends on ingestion and dermal absorption only from drinking water. *Among the population with habits of using swimming pools, the total cancer risk from THMs compounds is based on ingestion and dermal absorption from both drinking water and swimming pool water.

Chronic Hazard Index

Chronic Hazard Index for THMs compounds due to ingestion and dermal absorption from both drinking water and swimming pool water was 1.04E-06 for average concentrations and 5.43E-06 for maximum concentrations (Table 9). The chronic exposure index presented according to the intake route (ingestion and dermal absorption) did not

exceed the recommended limit value (one) for both average and maximum values. The THMs and their compounds in drinking water and swimming pool water on the City of Novi Sad territory would not cause the occurrence of the diseases even among the vulnerable population. Similar results were obtained by researchers in Taiwan, Arizona, Hong Kong, and Turkey (Lee et al., 2004; Panyakapo et al., 2008, Baytak et al., 2008).

Table 9: Chronic Hazard Index for THMs compounds due to ingestion and dermal absorption from both drinking water and swimming pool water in the City of Novi Sad, 2017.

Total THMs and compounds	Chronic Hazard Index after ingestion	Chronic Hazard Index after dermal absorption	Chronic Hazard Index
Assessment based on average concentration			
Chloroform	6.79E-07	5.30E-09	6.84E-07
Bromdichlormethane	8.32E-08	4.08E-10	8.36E-08
Dibromchlormethane	1.35E-07	5.68E-10	1.36E-07
Bromoform	1.30E-07	5.22E-10	1.31E-07
Total THMs	1.03E-06	6.79E-09	1.04E-06
Assessment based on maximum concentration			
Chloroform	4.26E-06	3.44E-08	4.29E-06
Bromdichlormethane	3.08E-07	1.68E-09	3.10E-07
Dibromchlormethane	4.70E-07	2.40E-09	4.72E-07
Bromoform	3.54E-07	1.43E-09	3.55E-07
Total THMs	5.39E-06	3.99E-08	5.43E-06

Conclusions

Based on our research, it can be concluded that:

- According to semi-quantitative risk characterization, the THMs concentration and occurrence in swimming pools water represents the very high risk, influencing the mortality of population, which indicates the need for quantitative risk characterization;
- According to quantitative risk characterization, the total cancer risk from exposure to THMs after the ingestion and dermal absorption is acceptable as for average, so for maximum concentration;
- Chronic Hazard Index is less than one, so THMs compounds are unlikely to cause the occurrence of diseases connected to THMs, even among the sensitive population;
- In the structure of total cancer risk for maximum concentration, as in the structure of Chronic Hazard Index for average and maximum THMs concentrations, chloroform, possible carcinogenic compound, is dominant;
- Adequate risk management for reducing the risk, especially within swimming pools, is necessary;
- Further investigation considering inhalation pathway and specific national data, instead of internationally used ones, is recommended.

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References

- Abdullah, A.M. (2014). Assessment of Potential Risks from Trihalomethanes in Water Supply at Alexandria Governorate. *J Pollut Eff Cont.* 2(2): 4 pages: 119 doi: 10.4172/2375-4397.1000119.
- Bartram, J., Corrales, L., Davison, A., Deere, D., Drury, D. and B. Gordon (2009). Water safety plan manual: step-by-step risk management for drinking-water suppliers. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.
- Baytak, D., Sofuoglu, A., Inal, F. and S.C. Sofuoglu (2008). Seasonal variation in drinking water concentrations of disinfection by-products in IZMIR and associated human health risks. *Science of the Total Environment.* (407): 286-96.
- Benford, D. (2001). Principles of risk assessment of food and drinking water related to human health. ILSI Europe Concise Monograph Series [monograph on the Internet], Brussels (Belgium): International Life Sciences Institute; [cited 2018 September 15]. Available from: http://ilsi.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2016/06/C2001Prin_Risk.pdf
- Bijelović, S., Jevtić, M., Dragić, N., Živadinović, E., Lukić, D. and D. Medić (2017). Risk assessment of drinking water from public wells. *Med Pregl; LXX* (9-10): 297-306.
- Bozym, M., Wzorek, M. and I. Klosok-Bazan (2017). Health risk as a consequence of exposure to trihalomethanes in swimming pool water. *Rocz Panstw Zakl Hig.* 68(4):331-337.
- Council Directive 98/83/EEC on the quality of water intended for human consumption. *Official Journal* 1998 L330;41:32.
- Council Directive 2000/60/EC establishing a framework for the Community action in the field of water policy. *Official Journal* 2000; L 327.
- Council Directive 2006/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 February 2006 concerning the management of bathing water quality and repealing Directive 76/160/EEC. *Official Journal* 2006; February 15th, 2006; L 64.
- Drev, D., Krivograd Klemenčič, A., Škarja, J. and J. Panjan (2015). Contamination of Bathing Waters with Trihalomethanes in Slovenia. *Zdrav Vestn.* (84): 659-69.
- Dyck, R., Sadiq, R., Rodriguez, M.J., Simard, S. and R. Tardif (2011). Trihalomethane exposures in indoor swimming pools: a level III fugacity model. *Water Research*, 45(16): 5084–98.
- Egorov, A.I., Tereschenko, A.A., Altshul, L.M., Vartiainen, T., Samsonov D. and B. LaBrecque et al. (2003). Exposures to drinking water chlorination by-products in a Russian city. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 206(6):539-51.
- Font-Ribera, L., Kogevinas, M., Nieuwenhuijsen, M.J., Grimalt, J.O. and C.M. Villanueva (2010). Patterns of water use and exposure to trihalomethanes among children in Spain. *Environmental Research.* 110: 571–579.
- Health Service Executive (HSE) and the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) (2011). Joint Position Statement on Trihalomethanes in Drinking Water. United States (U.S.) Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Washington, DC
- IARC (2013). IARC monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans, volume 101. Some chemicals in industrial and

- consumer products, some food contaminants and flavourings, and water chlorination by-products. International Agency for Research on Cancer, Lyon, France.
- IARC (2018). IARC monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans. List of classifications, Volumes 1-122, volume 101. [monograph on the Internet], Lyon (France): International Agency for Research on Cancer; [cited 2018 September 15]. Available from: <https://monographs.iarc.fr/list-of-classifications-volumes/>
- Lee, S.C., Guo, H., Lam, S.M.J. and S.L.A. Lau (2004). Multipathway risk assessment on disinfection by-products of drinking water in Hong Kong. *Environmental Research*, 94: 47–56.
- Luks-Betlej, K. and D. Bodzek (2002). Occurrence of Trihalomethanes, Particularly Those Containing Bromine, in Polish Drinking Waters. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*.11(3): 255-260.
- National Research Council (2001). Review of the US Navy's Human Health Risk Assessment of the Naval Air Facility at Atsugi, Japan. [monograph on the Internet], Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; [cited 2018 September 17th]. Available from <https://doi.org/10.17226/10053>
- Nieuwenhuijsen, M.J., Toledano, M.B. and P. Elliott (2000). Uptake of chlorination disinfection by-products; a review and a discussion of its implications for exposure assessment in epidemiological studies. *J Expo Anal Environ Epidemiol*. Nov-Dec, 10(6 Pt 1): 586-99.
- Official Gazette of Republic of Serbia (41/2009). Law on Food Safety.
- Official Gazette of Republic of Serbia (136/2020). Law on Protection of the Population from Infectious Diseases.
- Official Gazette of Republic of Serbia (42/1998, 44/1999, 28/2019). Rulebook on hygienic corectness of drinking water.
- Official Gazette of Republic of Serbia (97/2017). Rulebook on pool water safety.
- Panyakapo, M., Soontornchai, S. and P. Paopuree (2008). Cancer risk assessment from exposure to trihalomethanes in tap water and swimming pool water. *Journal of Environmental Science*. 20: 371-78.
- Paopuree, P., Panyakapo, M. and S. Soontornchai. Multi-pathway cancer risk assessment of Trihalomethanes exposure from chlorinated tap water and indoor swimming pool. [cited 2018 September 17]. Available from: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5560402/>
- Richardson, S.D., Plewa, M.J., Wagner, E.D., Schoeny, R. and D.M. Demarini (2007). Occurrence, genotoxicity, and carcinogenicity of regulated and emerging disinfection by-products in drinking water: a review and roadmap for research. *Mutat Res.*, Nov-Dec; 636 (1-3):178-242.
- Ristoiu, D., von Gunten, U., Mocan, A., Chira, R., Siegfried, B. and M. Haydee Kovacs et al. (2009). Trihalomethane formation during water disinfection in four water supplies in the Somes river basin in Romania. *Environ Sci Pollut Res*. 16 (Suppl 1):S55–S65.
- Safe Drinking Water Committee, National Research Council. *Drinking Water and Health, Volume 7 Disinfectants and Disinfectant By-Products* [monograph on the Internet], Washington, DC: National Academies Press; 1987 [cited 2018 September 15]. Available from: <http://www.nap.edu/catalog/1008.html>
- Salas, L.A., Cantor, K.P., Tardon, A., Serra, C., Carrato, A. And R. Garcia-Closas (2013). Biological and Statistical Approaches for Modeling Exposure to Specific Trihalomethanes and Bladder Cancer Risk. *Am J Epidemiol*.178(4):652–660.
- Sbutega Milošević, G (2014). Sanitarna higijena [Sanitary hygiene], 277-284, in: Higijena sa medicinskom ekologijom [Hygiene with medical ecology], Jorga, J., (eds). Medicinski fakultet Univerziteta u Beogradu, Beograd.
- Schmoll, O (2018). Drinking-water safety in the global and European policy context. on Workshop on developing a national roadmap towards scaling-up water safety plans in Serbia, EUSRB1813979/9.2/66408/1. Belgrade, Serbia.
- Szegedi Vízmű Zrt (2018). Quality and composition of the drinking water in Szeged. [homepage on the Internet]. Available from: http://www.szegedvizmu.hu/en/environmental_protection/quality_and_composition_of_the_drinking_water_in_szeged/
- Simard, S., Tardif, R. and M.J. Rodriguez (2013). Variability of chlorination by-product occurrence in water of indoor and outdoor swimming pools. *Water Res*. 47(5): 1763-1772.
- SRPS EN 15975-2:2015. Security of drinking water supply - Guidelines for risk and crisis management - Part 2: Risk management
- Summerhayes, R.J. (2014). Exposure to trihalomethanes in drinking water and small for gestational age births in New South Wales, Australia. [PhD thesis]. Southern Cross

- University, Lismore, NSW.
- Tardif R., Catto C. Haddad S., Simard S. and M. Rodriguez (2016). Assessment of air and water contamination by disinfection by-products at 41 indoor swimming pools. *Environ Res*, 148, 411-420.
- UNECE and WHO Regional office for Europe (2013). Water and health in Hungary. The third session of the Meeting of the parties to the protocol on water and health. Oslo, Norway.
- United Nations General Assembly (2016). Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 17 December 2015 [on the report of the Third Committee (A/70/489/Add.2)]:70/169, The human rights to safe drinking water and sanitation. A/RES/70/169.
- United States Environment Protection Agency (1987a). Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS) on dibromochloromethane, CASRN 124-48-1. National Center for Environmental Assessment of the United States (U.S.) Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). Washington, DC: Last revision from United States Environment Protection Agency in 2002.
- United States Environment Protection Agency (1987b). Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS) on bromoform, CASRN 75-25-2. National Center for Environmental Assessment of the United States (U.S.) Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). Washington, DC: Last revision from United States Environment Protection Agency in 2002.
- United States Environment Protection Agency (1988). Risk Assessment Guidance for Superfund Volume I, Human Health Evaluation Manual (Part A), Interim Final. Office of Emergency and Remedial Response, United States (U.S.) Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Washington, DC. 2010. Annotated version of the Risk Assessment Guidance for Superfund (RAGS) Part A. United States Environmental Protection Agency.
- United States Environment Protection Agency (2005). Guidelines for Carcinogen Risk Assessment.: Risk Assessment Forum United States (U.S.) Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Washington, DC.
- United States Environment Protection Agency (2010). Comprehensive Disinfectants and Disinfection Byproducts Rules (Stage 1 and Stage 2): Quick Reference Guide. Office of Water United States (U.S.) Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Water, Washington, DC.
- United States Environment Protection Agency (2012). Recreational water quality criteria. Health and Ecological Criteria Division, Office of Science and Technology, United States (U.S.) Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Water, Washington, DC.
- United States Environment Protection Agency (2018). 2018 Edition of the Drinking Water Standards and Health Advisories. EPA 822-F-18-001. Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Water U.S., Washington, DC.
- Viana, R.B., Cavalcante, M., Braga, F.M.G., Viana, A.B., Araujo, J.C. and R.F. Nascimento et al. (2009). Risk assessment of trihalomethanes from tap water in Fortaleza, Brazil. *Environ Monit Assess*. 151:317–325.
- v.Veldhoven, K., Keski-Rahkonen, P., Barupal, D.K., Villanueva, C.M., Font-Ribera, L. And A. Scalbert et al. (2018). Effects of exposure to water disinfection by-products in a swimming pool: A metabolome-wide association study. *Environment International*. 111: 60–70.
- World Health Organization (2005). Preventing Travelers' Diarrhoea: How to Make Drinking Water Safe. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland
- World Health Organization (2006). Guidelines for safe recreational water environments. Volume 2, Swimming pools and similar environments. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.
- World Health Organization (2017a). Guidelines for drinking-water quality: fourth edition incorporating the first addendum. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.
- WHO Regional Office for Europe (2017b). Improving drinking-water supply in rural areas of Serbia. World Health Organization, Copenhagen, Denmark.
- World Health Organization and the United Nations Children's Fund (2017). Progress on Drinking Water, Sanitation and Hygiene: 2017 Update and SDG Baselines. World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), Geneva, Switzerland.